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THE ESSENCE AND THEORETICAL BASES OF MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF THE ENTERPRISES

СУТНІСТЬ ТА ТЕОРЕТИЧНІ ОСНОВИ УПРАВЛІННЯ ЗОВНІШНЬОЕКОНОМІЧНОЮ ДІЯЛЬНІСТЮ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ

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Каталан С.М. Сутність та теоретичні основи управління зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю підприємств. Оглядова стаття.

В статті досліджено теоретичні та методичні питання визначення сутності та значення управління зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю. В результаті розгляду підходів сучасних авторів зроблено висновок, що під зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю агропромислового формувань слід розуміти взаємовигідні економічні відносини українських та іноземних підприємств, які пов'язані із забезпеченням всіма видами ресурсів, виробництвом і доведенням до споживача продукції агропромислового комплексу. Під управлінням зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю агропромислових формувань запропоновано розуміти активний вплив управлінського апарату агропромислових формувань на взаємовигідні економічні відносини українських та іноземних підприємств, які пов'язані із забезпеченням всіма видами ресурсів, виробництвом і доведенням до споживача агропромислової продукції з метою досягнення бажаних параметрів діяльності агропромислових формувань.

Ключові слова: зовнішньоекономічна діяльність, агропромислові формування, економічні відносини, управління зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю, агропромисловий комплекс, організаційно-економічні умови

Kaptalan S.M. The essence and theoretical bases of management of foreign economic activity of enterprises. Review article.

The article deals with theoretical and methodological issues of determining the essence and importance of foreign economic activity management. As a result of consideration of the approaches of modern authors concluded that under foreign trade activities the agroindustrial formations should be understood mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are connected with providing all kinds of resources, production and finishing to the consumer of agricultural products. Under the management of foreign economic activity of the agro-industrial units proposed to understand the impacts of the administrative apparatus of the agro-industrial units on mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are connected with providing all kinds of resources, production and finishing to the consumer of agricultural products with the aim of achieving the desired parameters of agro-industrial formations.

Keywords: foreign economic activity, agro-industrial formations, economic relations, management of foreign economic activity, agro-industrial complex, organizational and economic conditions

Modern conditions of functioning of the enterprises of agro-industrial complex of Ukraine testifies to increase of their dependence on results and efficiency of foreign economic activity. In connection with the above, the most important question is the analysis of the theoretical foundations of the process of foreign economic management and the definition of factors that necessitate the participation of agro-industrial formations of Ukraine in foreign economic activity.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Theoretical and methodological issues of determining the nature and importance of foreign economic activity management is the subject of research of many domestic and foreign scientists, in particular F. Taylor, A. Fayol, G. Weber, E. Durkheim, V. Pareto, G. Kunz, S. Odonnel, E. Dale, G. Tanenbaum, F. Masaryk, K. Barnard, V. Bakke, E. Trista, A. Emery, A. Rice and others. Among the authors who have given considerable attention to organizational and economic control components can distinguish L. Abalkina, I. Gontareva, L. Klimenko, I. Kryukov, A. Litvinova, Y. Luzan, N. Mazur, S. Modernogo, V. Ponomarenko, E. Yastremsky, B. Lukovskogo, O. Sekino, A. Yakovlev and others. However, despite the large number of studies, some theoretical and practical problems of management of foreign economic activity of agro-industrial formations remain unresolved. In particular, the terminological apparatus and components of the organizational and economic support for the management of foreign economic activity are not fully defined, which leads to confusion and errors when considering this problem.

The aim of the article is summarizing the essence of foreign economic activity of enterprises of agroindustrial formations, determination of features of the external environment of the agro-industrial groups in Ukraine that lead to their active participation in foreign trade activities.

The main part

Since Agroindustrial formations (further-AIF) carry out the activity taking into account features of

their external environment. Among the main external factors of the activity of the AIF, it is possible to single out the peculiarities of demand for agro-industrial products. According to N.D. Yankiv, AIF of Ukraine should take into account long-term global trend of increasing geographic specialization of production and, as consequence, increase in volumes of foreign economic activity (hereinafter – FEA) in the agro-industrial sector [1]. Geographical specialization of agricultural production is associated with natural climatic features, accompanied by a decrease in regional differences in the consumption of agricultural products, as a consequence, the share of those products that are not produced in the region increases [2].

This is happening in the context of lagging growth rates of agricultural production in the world compared to the rate of population growth, which leads to an increase in demand for food on world markets. One of the important external factors of activity of AIF in Ukraine is the ongoing process of globalization, any economic activity in the world that is reflected in the reduction of trade barriers of all kinds and increase the impact of AIF on foreign markets [3].

It is necessary to take into account not only the demand from foreign consumers of AIF but also the peculiarities of changes in demand for agricultural products in Ukraine. Over the past 10 years, the population of Ukraine has decreased by 10 million people, which led to a significant reduction in domestic demand for agricultural products. Such a drop could compensate for the increase in the level of solvency of the population, but, unfortunately, economic and political crises only worsen the standard of living of the population of Ukraine. Thus, a negative external factor in the development of the AIF is the reduction of the domestic market due to the decrease in the population of Ukraine.

Also, a feature of the demand of AIF for Ukraine is that the share of processed products of agricultural origin is constantly increasing in contrast to the share of purely raw products. This makes it necessary to deepen the integration of agricultural and industrial enterprises.

An additional foreign economic component of the increase in demand for the products of AIF of Ukraine is the global trend to replace hydrocarbon fuel with biofuels. As a result, in the world, including in Ukraine, the volume of production and foreign trade in such types of agro-industrial products as rapeseed, sunflower, soybeans, and products and waste of their processing increases.

Another external factor in the activities of the AIF is a significant increase in the efficiency of agricultural activities, which makes it possible to significantly increase the volume of agricultural production in Ukraine. A significant increase in production opportunities requires an expansion of the share in the old and the search for new, primarily foreign markets [4]. In addition to the need to enter new foreign markets, AIF require significant

investment, which is quite difficult to find in Ukraine, which is another factor in the high relevance of foreign economic activity of AIF.

Thus, the factors determining the need to participate in the foreign trade of the AIF of Ukraine are the following:

- increasing the efficiency and volume of agricultural production;
- stagnation of the domestic market of agro-industrial products;
- increased specialization of agro-industrial production in the world;
- reducing the specialization of consumption of agro-industrial products in the world;
- outpacing the population growth rate over the growth rate of agricultural production in the world;
- globalization of production and trade of agro-industrial products in the world;
- the tendency for biofuels to replace hydrocarbon fuels (see fig. 1).

It can be concluded that the peculiarities of the external environment of the Ukrainian AIF cause their active participation in foreign trade. Historically, the prerequisites for foreign trade of domestic enterprises were laid in the period of "perestroika". In 1987, the decentralization of foreign trade was announced with the provision of opportunities for enterprises to engage in foreign trade [5].

When Ukraine gained its independence, among the first laws was adopted the Law of Ukraine of April 16, 1991 "on foreign economic activity", which established the General basis of this activity [6]. Also at the state level, the conditions for the implementation of foreign trade taxation, in particular the value added tax, excise duty, duty and customs duties are defined. The regime of licensing and quotas of export-import operations for certain types of agricultural products has been defined.

The procedure for foreign trade AIF regulated by the Laws of Ukraine "on customs in Ukraine", "on the Single customs tariff", the Customs Code of Ukraine [7-9]. Presidential decree "on the application of International rules for the interpretation of commercial terms" [10]. Special attention should be paid to the International rules of interpretation of commercial terms, known as "INCOTERMS-2010" [11]. These rules were developed by the international chamber of Commerce and entered into force on 01.01.2011. In "INCOTERMS-2010" set out a clear interpretation of the eleven main trade terms, which makes it possible to simplify the process of determining the conditions of foreign trade [12-13].

In General, methods of regulation of foreign trade of economic entities are divided into two groups: administrative and economic. Administrative methods are fiscal, restrictive and set for a short period of time. While economic methods, as noted L. V. Klimenko, are long-term and the highest manner, promote the development of foreign economic activity [15].

Fig. 1. Factors that determine the relevance and necessity of participation of agro-industrial formations of Ukraine in foreign economic activity

Source: own elaboration

However, the formed legislative field of foreign trade for a long time did not lead to its active application by the AIF. Lack of conditions and infrastructure of activity of the agrarian market in Ukraine that led to chaoticness and opacity of wholesale trade in agricultural production was the reason of insufficient level of development of foreign economic activity of AIF. A partial solution to this problem was launched in 2000 with the issuance of The presidential Decree "on priority measures for the formation and functioning of the agricultural market", which allowed to protect producers from the actual monopoly of intermediary firms in foreign trade [14].

In today's time most of the AIF have a particular relevance to foreign trade, which can be considered at four levels: 1) at the level of the Supreme bodies of state power; 2) at the level of sectoral ministries and departments; 3) at the level of specialised foreign economic organisations; 4) at the level of individual AIF of Ukraine [4]. The subject of the study is to analyze the characteristics and problems of foreign trade at the fourth level – at the level of individual ACE.

L.O. Lisova believes that the evolution of views on foreign economic activity has historically passed three stages. At the first stage (up to the XIX century inclusive) FEA was based on classical descriptive concepts. At the second stage (mid 70-ies of XX art.) they were replaced by the theory of state regulation of foreign trade. The third stage (the end of XX art.) is characterized by a systematic approach to foreign trade management [16].

It can be concluded that the foreign trade of the AIF in modern conditions is based on the achievements of the classics of Economics (the theory

of absolute advantages of A. Smith, the theory of relative advantages of D. Ricardo and G. Torrence, the theory of international value of J.St. mill, the works of the monetarists and J.M. Keynes, Heckscher-Ohlin theory, Truda. Tugan-Baranovskogo and Leontief), and the modern achievements of scientists and development economists of large transnational corporations.

Consider in more detail the views of modern scientists on the essence of foreign trade enterprises. Some authors define FEA as a set of legal acts and mechanisms that ensure interaction between domestic and foreign enterprises, but this translates the discussion into a purely legal field instead of an economic one [17].

Other scientists focus on the fact that foreign trade is economic cooperation of economic entities from different countries. So, L.M. Simachenko notes that the FEA is a set of economic relations and contacts between enterprises in different countries, formed under the influence of foreign economic policy of the state [18]. S.P. Polishchuk believes that FEA is a component of business enterprise and the main direction of the implementation and improvement of international cooperation [19]. However, the authors do not focus on the nature of cooperation between enterprises of different countries, on what can be attributed to foreign trade.

More specific definition is offered in the works of M. Shuan and L.M. Fedorets [20-21]. M. Shuan defines the foreign trade as a completely independent activity of the AIF on the choice of foreign partners, product, price, volumes, terms and other conditions of export-import operations. L.M. Fedorets under FEA understands a set of activities of the AIF of all forms

of ownership, which are aimed at interacting with foreign partners and contractors in order to make a profit.

It should be noted that these authors pay priority attention to the export-import orientation, or trade with foreign partners for profit. While the foreign trade of the AIF can also refer to the process of providing all kinds of resources, primarily financial and technical. This draws the attention of G.M. Ginesin, I.B. Crow, who noted that the FEA AIF should include the activities associated not only with the implementation of export-import transactions and foreign capital inflow [22].

The most complete, in our opinion, is the definition of FEA AIF, given in the work of Sm Kvashi. Foreign trade in agro-industrial complex (further – AIC) of Ukraine, the author proposes to consider as mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign subjects of economic activities that take place in Ukraine and abroad and economic environment which is AIC [23]. The only thing that should be added, in our opinion, is a clarification of the nature of the relationship.

As a result of consideration of the approaches of contemporary authors to the conclusion that the FEA of AIF should be understood mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are connected with providing all kinds of resources, production and finishing to the consumer of agricultural products.

Another important theoretical issue is the generalization of scientists' views on the concept of "foreign trade management" AIF. The classics of modern control theory are F. Taylor, A. Fayol, M. Weber, E. Durkheim, V. Pareto, G. Kunz, S. Odonnel, E. Dale, G. Tanenbaum, F. Masaryk, K. Barnard, W. Bakke, E.L. Trist, A. Emery, A. Rice and others. Management as one of types of functional activity of the enterprise is rather well defined category not only foreign, but also domestic scientists [24-32]. Under management in General, it is customary to understand the active influence of the subject of management on the parameters of the management object in order to achieve the desired parameters by means of certain management actions.

Various approaches to understanding the essence and analysis of management as an economic category have been formed in the scientific literature. H. Kunz and S. Odonnel propose the following grouping of these approaches: 1) empirical, based on the analysis of concrete situations; 2) interpersonal relations; 3) how group behavior; 4) how cooperowen social system; 5) how socoteco system; 6) how the decision-making process; 7) how the information exchange process; 8) scientific management; 9) operating [33]. There are also system, process, sociological and other approaches.

Management of such sphere of the enterprise as foreign trade has certain features in comparison with other types of activity. First, a special area, the level of activity of the enterprise-international. Secondly, a wider geographical scope of activities, long distances,

other natural, climatic, cultural, temporary conditions of activity. Third, economic entities with different internal economic, political and legal conditions of activity participate in foreign trade activities. Fourth, the full subject of foreign trade are not only individual enterprises, but also directly to the state, as they establish certain requirements, restrictions on the movement of goods across their borders, set duties, subsidies, quotas for certain commodity groups, which is a significant tool for managing foreign trade enterprises [34]. It should be added that the issue of supporting foreign trade enterprises is one of the main tasks in the economic policy of the state in the modern conditions of globalization of the world economy, which will be given special attention in this study.

Foreign trade management is considered by scientists at several levels. At the national, regional and enterprise levels. Under the management of foreign economic activity at the macro level understand the impacts of the authorities (state, regional) for the subjects of foreign economic activity, is carried out with the help of administrative and economic instruments, in order to streamline their activities and achieve political and/or economic purposes [36].

This study will focus on the analysis of the FEA management process at the micro level. Based on the nature and category of "management" at the level of individual enterprises, under the management of foreign trade of the AIF we propose to understand the active impact of the management apparatus of the AIF on mutually beneficial economic relations of Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are associated with the provision of all kinds of resources, production and delivery to the consumer of agricultural products in order to achieve the desired parameters of the AIF.

Thus, one of the key issues in the process of management of foreign economic activity of AIF is the definition of certain desired parameters of activity or management targets to create organizational and economic conditions for their achievement. According to V.V. Yurchishin, the purpose of foreign trade management of the AIF is to increase the organizational and economic efficiency of foreign trade [37]. According to I.O. the Hook, the main reason of low efficiency of APF Ukraine is an imperfect economic mechanism [38]. We can fully agree with the opinion of the author that the improvement of organizational and economic support is one of the main conditions for achieving the goals of foreign trade management of agricultural enterprises.

FEA management, as well as any other activity, must comply with certain principles, be based on methods and ensure the implementation of scientifically based functions or management tasks. Consider the principles of foreign trade enterprise management. The most complete composition of the principles of foreign trade defined G.O. Gerasimenko, which, according to the author, consist of the

following:

- consistency-development of a set of measures necessary for the implementation of the project;
- process-consistency of actions in the process of activity, taking into account feedbacks;
- dynamism-adaptability to changes in the external and internal environment, manifested as the relationship of different methods of work and factors of influence;
- purposefulness – establishing relationships between the needs, interests of the enterprise and the goals of specific foreign economic projects;
- sociality-the acquisition of foreign trade enterprises of social significance;
- phasing-display the sequence of accumulation of information during the passage of certain stages;
- complexity-development of a set of interrelated projects that need to be implemented in order to implement the main project;
- selectivity-selection of the most promising foreign economic projects, taking into account the features of scientific and technological progress and economic and political situation;
- hierarchy-representation of foreign trade processes and projects in hierarchical subordination in accordance with the levels of management of the enterprise;
- multivariance-preparation of alternative solutions for the choice of means to achieve foreign trade goals and the definition of alternative foreign trade goals;
- independence – providing independence in decision-making and responsibility for their consequences;
- orientation-management orientation to the needs of the external market.

Management of foreign trade of the enterprise should be based on compliance with all the principles of management, since the mismatch of management to these principles can lead to a decrease in the efficiency of the management system and, as a consequence, reduce the efficiency of foreign trade of the enterprise.

Next, we consider methods of management of foreign economic activity of enterprise, understood as a set of methods, tools and techniques of influence on the foreign trade enterprises [39]. L.K. Kozhevnikova proposes to divide all the methods of management of foreign economic activity into three groups: economic, administrative and socio-psychological [34]. The economic methods include a system of economic measures, levers of influence on managed objects in order to achieve this goal. Economic methods provide unity of economic interests of two subjects of activity. The economic methods of foreign trade management include the stimulation of staff to work effectively, consumers to purchase products, partners to cooperate, society to a positive attitude to the enterprise. Economic methods of foreign trade management differ from others in that they are based on the assumption of the possibility and the need for

bilateral, mutually beneficial cooperation between the subjects of foreign trade in order to achieve the goals and meet the economic interests of the subjects in parallel.

The disadvantage of economic methods is that some traders do not act in accordance with their own interests. For example, public authorities can act in the interests of individual entrepreneurs, and not in the interests of society and the personnel of the enterprise may not respond to incentives from cervista since, for example, may not have the desire to earn more than they need for current purposes (until such time as the staff will not develop new requirements) that will lead to a lack of the desired counter-reaction to economic methods of management of foreign economic activity of the enterprise.

In cases where the economic methods of foreign trade management do not have the desired performance, come into force administrative methods of management, which are based on a certain coercive nature of the interaction of foreign trade entities. Administrative methods of management include regulation, rationing, legal restriction through contracts and agreements, and the like. Thanks to the administrative methods of foreign trade management, the enterprise can provide a more predictable reaction of other foreign trade entities to its management actions.

The disadvantages of administrative methods of foreign trade is not the possibility of their use in relation to all subjects of foreign trade, since all of them except the staff, do not have to comply with administrative orders and may refuse to draw up legal contracts that will limit their activities. Deficiencies in the administrative techniques of foreign trade is the opposite reaction of resistance on the part of subjects of foreign economic activity on the methods of administrative control that is associated with the natural desire of every person to freedom of will.

Socio-psychological methods of foreign trade management are based on the establishment of personal relationships and relationships between the subjects of foreign trade. Socio-psychological methods of management are also called informal methods, because they are based on the moral and psychological motives of the foreign trade entities, such as the desire for interaction, communication, moral encouragement, internal development and confidence, psychological stability and others. The disadvantage of socio-psychological methods of foreign trade management is that it can be an advantage – informality. The negative side of the informality of this group of management methods is that the reaction to these management methods are unpredictable and their effectiveness depends entirely on the personality of the Manager.

None of the groups of methods of foreign trade management has complete superiority over others and has certain disadvantages. The management of the enterprise shall use management methods of all types according to those circumstances and tasks which are put before the enterprise in each separate case. Only

the complexity of the use of management methods will allow to obtain optimal results of foreign trade enterprises.

The last component of foreign trade management of the enterprise is the definition of its functions. Modern scientists pay much attention to this issue but still have not come to a common point of view [40-45]. O.G. Gerasimenko believes that the functions of management of foreign economic activity should enable constant updating of the product range and its manufacturing technology [41]. Yu.V. Makogon proposes to include export strategies, the production process and production relationships with domestic partners in the FEA functions [40]. L.E. Strowski adds to the aforementioned search functions and the creation of an export product, assess its competitiveness and ensure production requirements, planning and sourcing, ensuring internal resources [42]. However, the FEA functions given by the above-mentioned authors are rather specific tools, management tools than management functions.

Most scientists agree with the vision of the FEA management system as part of the overall management system of the enterprise, which necessitates subordination of FEA management functions to the General management functions. So, M.A. Ovsienko believes that the functions of management of foreign economic activity include the planning, organization, coordination, motivation, accounting, control and information provision. However, in our view, some of the proposed management functions can be combined. For example, organization with coordination, accounting with control. And information support in modern conditions is not a function of management, but only one of the components of such a function of the enterprise as the provision of resources. Without providing the enterprise with information resources, it is now impossible not only foreign economic, but also any business activity. Management is based on certain external and internal conditions of activity, including the provision of information resources.

A.M. Ovsienko separately allocates organizational and economic functions of foreign trade management. Which includes the choice of strategic directions of foreign trade, the choice of forms and methods of foreign trade, foreign trade planning, organization and coordination of foreign trade, marketing research, information support of foreign trade, accounting and control of foreign trade, motivation and development of personnel, financial management, commercial pricing [44]. Despite the unification of some functions into one group, the author increased their total number by adding to the management functions some other functions of the enterprise: production functions, functions of providing resources, marketing functions.

In general, the number of control functions may be increased depending on the desire of the author to clarify, to allocate them species, but it is possible to agree with L.K. Kozhevnikova, among which the management functions of the FEA proposes four main functions of management: planning, organization,

motivation and control [45]. Let us consider in more detail the content of each of the General FEA management functions.

FEA planning is to establish general and specific objectives of FEA enterprise based on the analysis of all components of the external and internal environment of the enterprise. The analysis of the external environment is complicated by the need to collect information on foreign markets. The FEA planning process should be based on the classical principles of planning, among which the principle of optimal tasks and plans with their parallel validity should be highlighted. Optimality means search and selection of the best task (plan) from all possible. Such a plan, which will most allow to fulfill the General objectives of the enterprise. The validity of foreign trade planning means that the enterprise should choose only those options of plans (tasks) that can be realistically performed taking into account external and internal factors, the main of which are the demand for products in foreign markets and the availability of production capabilities of the enterprise.

Organization of foreign trade is to structure foreign trade, establish the conditions and parameters of interaction between internal participants of foreign trade enterprises, as well as the interaction of internal and external subjects of foreign trade. Specific areas of organization of foreign trade:

- establishment of such types of organizational, General and production structures of the enterprise that will allow to obtain the best results of foreign trade;
- the choice of a legal form and form of ownership of the enterprise, which will provide the best conditions for the implementation of foreign trade;
- selection of territorial and sectoral structure of foreign trade enterprises with the establishment of territorial markets for foreign trade and their industry specialization.

Particularly important, in our opinion, is the function of motivation in the process of foreign trade. As stated in the scientific works of O.S. Litvinov and O.O. Sukach, motivation is to meet certain needs and interests of the individual [46]. The motivation of all subjects of foreign trade both within the enterprise and in the near and far external environment does not coincide, since economic needs are subjective. This leads to the need to develop a system of measures-incentives to encourage themselves and others to act to achieve their own economic interests in the process of foreign trade.

This activity is called the system of foreign trade incentives and consists of two types of incentives: moral and material. Material incentives are based on economic management methods and are aimed at bilateral achievement of economic interests of subjects in the process of foreign trade-profit, income.

However, it is also important to use moral incentives, which is based on socio-psychological methods of management and is aimed at achieving the

economic interests of the enterprise and the psychological, not economic interests of other subjects of foreign trade. Moral stimulation is the primary function of foreign trade management in the case when the subjects of foreign trade are not elastic to changes in profits, income, or in cases where the company can not offer satisfaction of economic interests of the subjects-partners of foreign trade at a better level than competitors [46].

Thus, the essence of foreign trade and its management activities was considered. Principles, methods and functions of FEA management are analyzed.

Consideration of the theoretical foundations of the process of management of foreign economic activity of AIF of Ukraine allowed to draw the following conclusions:

The factors that determine the need for the participation of the Ukrainian AIF in foreign trade, namely: increasing the efficiency and volume of agricultural production in Ukraine; stagnation of the domestic market of agricultural products in Ukraine; increasing the specialization of agricultural production in the world; reducing the specialization of consumption of agricultural products in the world; outstripping the growth rate of population growth over the growth rate of agricultural production in the world; globalization of production and trade of agricultural products in the world; the tendency to replace hydrocarbon fuels with biofuels.

The result is a critical examination of ideas of modern authors concluded that the FEA of AIF should be understood mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are connected with providing all kinds of resources, production and finishing to the consumer of agricultural products.

Under the management of foreign trade AIF proposed to understand the active impact of the management of the ACE on mutually beneficial

economic relations of Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are associated with the provision of all kinds of resources, production and delivery to the consumer products in order to achieve the desired parameters of the AIF.

Conclusions

In the process of considering the theoretical foundations of the process of management of foreign economic activity of AIF of Ukraine the following conclusions:

The factors that determine the need for the participation of the Ukrainian AIF in foreign trade, namely: increasing the efficiency and volume of agricultural production in Ukraine; stagnation of the domestic market of agricultural products in Ukraine; increasing the specialization of agricultural production in the world; reducing the specialization of consumption of agricultural products in the world; outstripping the growth rate of population growth over the growth rate of agricultural production in the world; globalization of production and trade of agricultural products in the world; the tendency to replace hydrocarbon fuels with biofuels;

The result is a critical examination of ideas of modern authors concluded that the FEA of AIF should be understood mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are connected with providing all kinds of resources, production and finishing to the consumer of agricultural products;

Under the management of foreign trade AIF proposed to understand the active impact of the management of the AIF on mutually beneficial economic relations of Ukrainian and foreign enterprises, which are associated with the provision of all kinds of resources, production and delivery to the consumer products in order to achieve the desired parameters of the AIF.

Abstract

This article is devoted to the study of theoretical and methodological issues of determining the nature and importance of management of foreign economic activity. It examines the determinants of the need for participation in foreign trade activities the agroindustrial formations in Ukraine and determined that the peculiarities of the agro-industrial groups of Ukraine are responsible to actively participate in foreign trade activities. As a result of the analysis of the approaches of modern authors concluded that under foreign trade activities the agroindustrial formations should be understood mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises related to the provision of all types of resources, manufacturing and bringing to the consumer of agricultural products. The views of scientists on the concept of "management of foreign economic activity" of agro-industrial formations are analyzed and summarized. Under the management of foreign economic activity of the agro-industrial units proposed to understand the impacts of the administrative apparatus of the agro-industrial units on mutually beneficial economic relations between Ukrainian and foreign enterprises related to the provision of all types of resources, manufacturing and bringing to the consumer of agricultural products with the aim of achieving the desired parameters of agro-formations. The key issues in the management of foreign economic activity of agro-industrial formations is to determine certain desired parameters of activity or management targets to create organizational and economic conditions for their achievement. The principles, methods and functions of management of foreign economic activity are defined.

Due to the increasing dependence of the enterprises of agro-industrial complex of Ukraine, today the question of the analysis of theoretical bases of process of management of foreign economic and definition of factors

which cause need of participation of agro-industrial formations of Ukraine in foreign economic activity arises urgent and urgent.

The question of determining the nature and importance of management of foreign economic activity is the subject of study of many domestic and foreign scientists, in particular F. Taylor, A. Fayol, G. Weber, E. Durkheim, V. Pareto, G. Kunz, S. Odonnel, E. Dale, G. Tanenbaum, F. Masaryk, K. Barnard, V. Bakke, E. Trista, A. emery, A. rice and others. However, despite the large number of studies, some theoretical and practical problems of management of foreign economic activity of agro-industrial formations remain unresolved. In particular, the terminological apparatus and components of the organizational and economic support for the management of foreign economic activity are not fully defined, which leads to confusion and errors when considering this problem.

This article aims at summarizing the essence of foreign economic activity of enterprises of agroindustrial formations, determination of features of the external environment of the agro-industrial groups in Ukraine that lead to their active participation in foreign trade activities.

Список літератури:

1. Янків М.Д. Організаційно-економічні механізми розвитку і функціонування АПК України / М.Д. Янків. – Львів: Коопосвіта. – 2000. – 431 с.
2. Шашло Н.В. Стратегія розвитку зовнішньоекономічної діяльності підприємств АПК України: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.00.04 «Економіка та управління підприємствами (за видами економічної діяльності)» / Н.В. Шашло. – Луганськ, 2009. – 24 с.
3. Фещенко О.М., Ільченко В.М. Управління потенціалом інноваційного розвитку підприємств АПК на експортних ринках // Маркетинг і менеджмент інновацій. – 2011. – №. 4 (2). – С. 229-236.
4. Черевко В.Д. Організаційно-правове забезпечення зовнішньоекономічної діяльності підприємств АПК // Науковий вісник Львівського національного університету ветеринарної медицини та біотехнологій ім. Гжицького. – 2011. – №. 13, № 4 (5). – С. 297-302.
5. Стеценко Ж.В. Структура і функції зовнішньоекономічного комплексу в реалізації економічної політики України. Режим доступу: http://www.rusnauka.com/5_NTSTB_2007/Economics/20062.doc.htm.
6. Закон України «Про зовнішньоекономічну діяльність». Режим доступу: <http://zakon2.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/959-12>.
7. Закон України «Про митну справу в Україні». Режим доступу: <http://zakon2.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1262-12>.
8. Закон України «Про Єдиний митний тариф». Режим доступу: <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2097-12>.
9. Закон України «Про митний кодекс». Режим доступу: <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/4495-17>.
10. Указ Президента Кераїни «Про використання Міжнародних правил інтерпретації комерційних термінів» URL: <http://zakon3.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/567/94>.
11. Инкотермс. Міжнародні правила тлумачення торговельних термінів Міжнародної торгової палати URL: http://zakon3.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/988_007.
12. Желнова К.В. Применение норм «Инкотермс 2010»: обязанности сторон по внешнеторговому контракту // Тренды развития современного общества: управленческие, правовые, экономические и социальные аспекты [Текст]: Сборник научных статей 4-й Международной научно-практической конференции (17-19 сентября 2014 года), редкол.: Горохов А.А. (отв. ред.). – Курск: Юго-Зап. гос. ун-т. – 2014. – 350 с.
13. Нейкова, Л.І. Управління збутом продукції агропідприємств-суб'єктів зовнішньоекономічної діяльності [Електронний ресурс] / Л.І. Нейкова, І.В. Круценко // Ефективна економіка. – 2013. - № 11. – Режим доступу до журналу: <http://www.economy.nauka.com.ua>.
14. Нещадим Л.М. Перспективні напрями покращення інфраструктурного забезпечення зовнішньоекономічної діяльності регіональних аграрних підприємств // Редакційна колегія. – 2015. – 110 с.
15. Механізм державного управління зовнішньоторговельною діяльністю аграрного сектора економіки України / Л.В. Клименко // Агросвіт. – 2013. – №2. – С. 6-10
16. Лісова Л.О. Розвиток зовнішньоекономічної діяльності підприємствами АПК Сумської області: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.00.04 «Економіка та управління підприємствами (за видами економічної діяльності)» / Л.О. Лісова. – Суми, 2008. – 18 с.

17. Сисоєва Т.П. Інструментарій теорії і практики оцінки зовнішньоекономічної діяльності регіону // Вісник Сумського національного аграрного університету. Серія «Економіка та менеджмент» / Т.П. Сисоєва. – 2007. – Вип. 6-7 (26-27). – С. 197-201.
18. Письмаченко Л.М. Державне управління зовнішньоторгівельною діяльністю в Україні: регулювання та контроль: [монографія] / Л.М. Письмаченко. – Донецьк: ТОВ «Юго-Восток, Лтд», 2008. – 366 с.
19. Поліщук С.П. Організаційні форми та економічна ефективність діяльності спільних сільськогосподарських підприємств: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.00.04 «Економіка та управління підприємствами (за видами економічної діяльності)» / С.П. Поліщук. – Київ, 2010. – 20 с.
20. Сфуан М. Шляхи підвищення ефективності ЗЕД підприємств АПК: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.00.04 «Економіка та управління підприємствами (за видами економічної діяльності)» / М. Сфуан. – Луганськ, 2010. – 20 с.
21. Федорець Л.М. Вектори стратегічного розвитку зовнішньоекономічної діяльності АПК регіону // Економіка АПК. – 2009. – №. 5. – С. 69-75.
22. Гринишин Г.М., Вороний І.В. Регіональні аспекти зовнішньоекономічної діяльності підприємств АПК // Економічні науки. Сер.: Облік і фінанси. – 2013. – №. 10 (1). – С. 3-8.
23. Кваша С.М. Формування фінансово-економічного механізму державного регулювання зовнішньоекономічної діяльності в АПК України: автореферат дисертації на здобуття наукового ступеня доктора економічних наук: спец. 08.07.02 – «Економіка сільського господарства і АПК» / С.М. Кваша. – Київ, 2001. – 41 с.
24. Бурнукін В.О. Формування системи управління зернопродуктовим підкомплексом [Електронний ресурс] / В.О. Бурнукін. – Режим доступу: http://archive.nbuv.gov.ua/portal/chem_bio/nuln.
25. Грабовецький Б.Є. Економічний аналіз: [Навч. посібник] / Б.Є. Грабовецького – К.: Центр учбової літератури, 2009. – 256 с.
26. Калетнік Г.М. Територіальна організація зернопродуктового комплексу регіону та напрями його удосконалення: [Монографія] / Г.М. Калетнік, Т.В. Пепа, В.М. Ціхановська. – Вінниця: Вінницька газета, 2010. – 180 с.
27. Крюкова І.О., Непочатенко В.О. Стратегія інноваційного розвитку пріоритетних галузей аграрного виробництва // Економіка: реалії часу. – 2013. – №. 4. – С. 133-141.
28. Кузнецова І.О. Визначення сутності дефініції // Вісник Київського національного торговельно-економічного університету. – 2009. – №. 1. – С. 55-62.
29. Лебедев К.А. Організаційно-економічний механізм розвитку зернопродуктового підкомплексу: теорія, методологія, практика: [монографія] / К.А. Лебедев. – К.: ННЦ «Ін-т аграрної економіки», 2009. – 272 с.
30. Митяй О.В. Організаційно-економічні механізми підвищення ефективності діяльності аграрних підприємств: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.00.04 «Економіка та управління підприємствами (за видами економічної діяльності)» / О.В. Митяй. – Умань, 2013. – 20 с.
31. Сімкова Т.О. Організаційно-економічне забезпечення управління якістю послуг аеропортів // Проблеми підвищення ефективності інфраструктури. – 2012. – Т. 28. – №. 28. – С. 2.
32. Яремчук Н.В. Методика оцінки ефективності управлінської діяльності в системі підприємств зернопродуктового під комплексу [Електронний ресурс] / Н.В. Яремчук // Ефективна економіка. – 2013. – №12. – Режим доступу до журналу: <http://www.economy.nauka.com.ua>.
33. Кунц Г. Управление: системный и ситуационный анализ управленческих функций: [монографія] / Г. Кунц, С. О'доннел. – М.: «Прогресс», 1981. – 496 с.
34. Свідерська А.В. Поняття та класифікація ризиків у зовнішньоекономічній діяльності підприємства / Антоніна Свідерська // Галицький економічний вісник – Тернопіль: ТНТУ, 2014. – Том 46. – № 3. – С. 113-121.
35. Твердохлеб Є.С. Особливості управління зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю підприємства [Електронний ресурс] / Є.С. Твердохлеб // Маркетинг: теорія і практика: зб. наук. пр. – Луганськ. – 2008. – № 14. – Режим доступу: http://esteticamente.ru/portal/Soc_Gum/Mtip/2008_14/index.html.
36. Федорець Л.М. Вектори стратегічного розвитку зовнішньоекономічної діяльності АПК регіону // Економіка АПК. – 2009. – №. 5. – С. 69-75.
37. Юрчишин В.В. Аграрна політика в Україні на зламах політичних епох: історико-соціально-економічні нариси / В.В. Юрчишин. – К.: Науково-виробниче підприємство «Видавництво «Наукова думка» НАН України», 2009. – 366 с.
38. Крюкова І.О. Організаційно-економічний механізм розвитку агроформувань в пореформений період [Текст]: автореф. дис. канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.07.02 – «Економіка сільського господарства і АПК» / І.О. Крюкова. – Х.: ХНАУ, 2006. – 20 с.
39. Овсієнко А.М. Управління зовнішньоекономічною діяльністю суб'єктів господарювання / Овсієнко А.М. // Экономический вестник университета. Сборник научных трудов ученых и аспирантов. – Переяслав-Хмельницький: ПХДПУ, 2015. – Том 27-1. – С.123-128.

40. Внешнеэкономическая деятельность предприятия: Англо-русский словарь-справочник / Под ред. Проф. Л.Е. Стровского. – М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2002. – 510 с.
41. Дроздова Г.М. Менеджмент зовнішньоекономічної діяльності підприємства: Навч. посібник. – К.: ЦУЛ, 2002. – 171 с.
42. Літвінов О.С. Ефективність витрат на оплату праці як фактор конкурентоспроможності підприємства [Текст]: / О.С. Літвінов, О.О. Сукач // Конкурентоспроможність підприємства: оцінка рівня та напрями підвищення: [монографія / за заг. ред. О.Г. Янкового]. – Одеса : Атлант, 2013. – 459-470 с.
43. Макогон Ю.В. Внешнеэкономическая деятельность: организация, управление, прогнозирование / Ю.В. Макогон. – 2-е изд., перераб. и доп. – Донецк: Альфа-пресс, 2004. – 343 с.
44. Рибаківа Т.О. Функції зовнішньоекономічної діяльності промислових підприємств / Т.О. Рибаківа // Культура народів Причорномор'я. – 2009. – №172. Т2. – С. 108-110.
45. Свідерська А.В. Поняття та класифікація ризиків у зовнішньоекономічній діяльності підприємства / Антоніна Свідерська // Галицький економічний вісник. Тернопіль: ТНТУ, 2014. – Том 46. – № 3. – С. 113-121.
46. Колесник В.М. Організаційні аспекти маркетингу у зернопродуктовому підкомплексі АПК / В.М. Колесник // Тези доповідей Причорноморської регіональної науково-практичної конференції. – Миколаїв, – 2006. – С. 36-38.

References:

1. Yankiv, M.D. (2000). Organizational and economic mechanisms of development and functioning of agriculture of Ukraine. Lviv: Coopest [in Ukrainian].
2. Shashlo, N.V. (2009). Strategy of development of foreign economic activity of the enterprises of agrarian and industrial complex of Ukraine: autoref. dis. for science. the degree candidate. Ekon. Sciences: spec. 08.00.04 "Economics and management of enterprises (for economic activities)". Lugansk [in Ukrainian].
3. Feshchenko, O.M., & Ilchenko, V.M. (2011). Potential management of innovative development of agricultural enterprises in export markets . Marketing and management innovatsiy, 4 (2), 229-236 [in Ukrainian].
4. Cherevko, V.D. (2011). Organizational and legal support of foreign economic activity of agricultural enterprises // Scientific journal of Lviv national University of veterinary medicine and biotechnology, 13, 4 (5), 297-302 [in Ukrainian].
5. Stetsenko, Zh.V. (2007). Structure and functions of the foreign economic complex in the implementation of economic policies. Retrieved from: http://www.rusnauka.com/5_NT5B_2007/Economics/20062.doc.htm [in Ukrainian].
6. The law of Ukraine "On foreign economic activity" Retrieved from: <http://zakon2.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/959-12> [in Ukrainian].
7. The law of Ukraine "On customs Affairs in Ukraine" Retrieved from: <http://zakon2.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1262-12> [in Ukrainian].
8. The law of Ukraine "On Unified customs tariff", Retrieved from: <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2097-12> [in Ukrainian].
9. The law of Ukraine" On Customs code " Retrieved from: <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/4495-17> [in Ukrainian].
10. Presidential decree "on the application of International rules for the interpretation of commercial terms" Retrieved from: <http://zakon3.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/567/94> [in Ukrainian].
11. Incoterms. International rules for the interpretation of trade terms of The international chamber of Commerce Retrieved from: http://zakon3.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/988_007 [in Ukrainian].
12. Zhelnova, K.V. (2014). Application of norms "Incoterms 2010": obligations of the parties under the foreign trade contract. Trends of development of modern society: administrative, legal, economic and social aspects: Collection of scientific articles of the 4th International scientific-practical conference (p.-350). Kursk: South-West. state UN-T [in Ukrainian].
13. Neikova, L.I. (2013). Sales Management of agricultural enterprises-subjects of foreign economic activity. Effective economy, 11. Retrieved from: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua> [in Ukrainian].
14. Neschadim, L.M. (2015). Promising directions of improvement of infrastructure support of foreign economic activity of regional agricultural enterprises [in Ukrainian].
15. Klimenko, L.V. (2013). The mechanism of state management of foreign trade activities of the agricultural sector of the economy of Ukraine. Agrosvit, 2, 6-10 [in Ukrainian].
16. Lesnaya, L.A. (2008). Development of foreign economic activity by agricultural enterprises of Sumy region: abstract. dis. for science. the degree candidate. Ekon. Sciences: spec. 08.00.04 "Economics and management of enterprises (for economic activities)". Sumy [in Ukrainian].

17. Sysoeva, T.P. (2007). Tools of theory and practice of evaluation of foreign economic activity of the region // Bulletin of Sumy national agrarian University. Series "Economics and management", 6-7, (26-27). (pp. 197-201) [in Ukrainian].
18. Pismichenko, L.M. (2008). State management of foreign trade activities in Ukraine: regulation and control. Donetsk: LLC "South-East, Ltd." [in Ukrainian].
19. Polishchuk, S.P. (2010). Organizational forms and economic efficiency of joint agricultural enterprises: abstract. dis. for science. the degree candidate. Ekon. Sciences: spec. 08.00.04 "Economics and management of enterprises (by type of economic activity)". Kyiv [in Ukrainian].
20. Shuan, M. (2010). Ways of increase of efficiency of foreign economic activity of agricultural enterprises: Avtoref. dis. for science. the degree candidate. Ekon. Sciences: spec. 08.00.04 "Economics and management of enterprises (by types of economic activity)". Lugansk [in Ukrainian].
21. Fedorets, L.M. (2009). Vectors of strategic development of foreign economic activity. Aroindustrial complex of the region, 5, (pp. 69-75) [in Ukrainian].
22. Grinishin, G.M., Voronoi, I.V. (2013). Regional aspects of foreign economic activity of agricultural enterprises. Economic Sciences. Ser.: Accounting and Finance, 10 (1), (pp. 3-8) [in Ukrainian].
23. Kvasha, S.M. (2011). Formation of financial and economic mechanism of state regulation of foreign economic activity in agriculture of Ukraine: abstract of the thesis for the degree of doctor of economic Sciences: spec. 08.07.02 "Economics of agriculture and agribusiness". Kiev [in Ukrainian].
24. Burmakin, V.A. Forming of the management system of the grain products subcomplex. Retrieved from: http://archive.nbuv.gov.ua/portal/chem_bio/nuln [in Ukrainian].
25. Grabovetsky, B.E. (2009). Economic analysis. Center educational literature [in Ukrainian].
26. Kaletnik, G.M. (2010). Territorial organization of grain products complex of the region and directions of its improvement. Vinnitsa: Vinnytsia newspaper [in Ukrainian].
27. Kryukova, I.A., Neochetina, V.A. (2013). The Strategy of innovative development of priority branches of agrarian production. Economy: reality time, 4, (pp. 133-141) [in Ukrainian].
28. Kuznetsova, I.O. (2009). Definitions of the essence of the definition. Bulletin of the Kiev national trade and economic University, 1, (pp. 55-62) [in Ukrainian].
29. Lebedev, K.A. (2009). Organizational and economic mechanism of grain subcomplex development: theory, methodology, practice. Kiyv: NSC "Institute of agrarian economy" [in Ukrainian].
30. Mityai, A.V. (2013). Organizational and economic mechanisms to improve the efficiency of agricultural enterprises: abstract. dis. for science. the degree candidate. Ekon. Sciences: spec. 08.00.04 "Economics and management of enterprises (by type of economic activity)". Uman [in Ukrainian].
31. Simkova, T.A. (2012). Organizational and economic support of quality management of airport services. Problems of improving the efficiency of infrastructure, 28, (p. 2) [in Ukrainian].
32. Yaremchuk, N.V. (2013). Methods of assessing the effectiveness of management activities in the system of enterprises of grain-producing complex. Effective economy, 12. Retrieved from: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua> [in Ukrainian].
33. Kunz, G., & O'donnell, S. (1981). Management: system and situational analysis of management functions. Moscow: "Progress" [in Ukrainian].
34. Sviderskiy, V.A. (2014) The Concept and classification of risks in foreign economic activity of the enterprise. Galician economic journal Ternopil : TNTU, 46, 3, (pp. 113-121) [in Ukrainian].
35. Tverdokhle, E.S. (2008). Features of management of foreign economic activity of the enterprise. Marketing: theory and practice: collection of Sciences. St. Lugansk. Retrieved from: http://esticamente.ru/portal/Soc_Gum/Mtip/2008_14/index.html. [in Ukrainian].
36. Fedorets, L.M. (2009). Vectors of strategic development of foreign economic activity of agroindustrial complex of the region, 5, (pp. 69-75) [in Ukrainian].
37. Yurchishin, V.V. (2009). Agrarian policy in Ukraine at the fractures of political eras: historical, socio-economic essays. Kiyv: Scientific and production enterprise "Publishing house" Naukova Dumka "NAS of Ukraine", (p. 366) [in Ukrainian].
38. Kryukova, I.A. (2006). Organizational and economic mechanism of development of agricultural formations in the post-reform period. Abstract. dis. Cand. Ekon. Sciences: spec. 08.07.02 "Economics of agriculture and agribusiness". Kharkiv, KNOW [in Ukrainian].
39. Ovsienko, A.M. (2015). Management of foreign economic activity of business entities. Economic journal of the University. Collection of scientific papers of scientists and postgraduates. Pereyaslav-Khmelnytsky: PDPU, 27-1, (pp. 123-128) [in Ukrainian].
40. Strovsky, L.E. (2002). Foreign economic activity of the enterprise: English-Russian dictionary. Moscow: UNITY-DANA, [in Ukrainian].
41. Drozdova, G.M. (2002). Management of foreign economic activity of the enterprise. Kharkiv: TSUL [in Ukrainian].
42. Litvinov, O.S. (2013) The effectiveness of expenditure on labor as a factor of competitiveness of the enterprise. Competitiveness of an enterprise: assessment of the level and areas of improvement. Odessa: Atlant [in Ukrainian].

43. Makogon, Yu.V. (2004). Foreign Economic activity: organization, management, forecasting. Donetsk: Alfa-press [in Ukrainian].
44. Rybakova, T.O. (2009). Functions of foreign economic activity of industrial enterprises. Culture of the peoples of the black sea region, 172, 2, (pp. 108-110) [in Ukrainian].
45. Sviderskiy, V.A. (2014). The Concept and classification of risks in foreign economic activity of the enterprise. Galician economic journal, Ternopil: TNTU, 46, 3, (pp. 113-121) [in Ukrainian].
46. Kolesnik, V.M. (2006). Organizational aspects of marketing in the grain subcomplex of agriculture. Abstracts of the black sea regional scientific-practical conference (pp. 36-38). Nikolaev [in Ukrainian].

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